

The Phenomenon of After-effect in certain Photochemical Reactions.

BY

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In previous papers (Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, 121, 1561; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1856) it has been mentioned that the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine is very sensitive to light. We have observed that a mixture of potassium oxalate and iodine when exposed to light and brought back to darkness shows a greater velocity in the dark than when the reacting mixture is not at all exposed to light. This phenomenon is known as "after-effect" in photochemical reactions.

The phenomenon of "after-effect" has already been noted in certain photochemical changes. In solvents other than alcohol the oxidation of iodoform as studied by Plotnikow (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1911, 76, 743) shows a marked after-effect when illumination has ceased. Trautz and Thomas (*Physik. Z.*, 1906, 7, 899; *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1907, 13, 550; *Z. Wiss. Phot.*, 1906, 4, 352) note after-effect of illumination in the photo-oxidation of sodium sulphide, of cuprous chloride in hydrochloric acid solution and of benzaldehyde. That the benzaldehyde oxidation shows an after-effect when illumination has been discontinued has been confirmed by Bäckström (Taylor's *Physical Chemistry*, p. 1247). Kistiakowski (*Z. physikal.*

Chem., 1900, 35, 431) observed an after-effect of illumination in the case of the photo-decomposition of hydrogen peroxide by visible light in presence of ferro- and ferricyanides.

With a view to test whether any after-effect of illumination takes place or not in photo-sensitive reactions we investigated a number of reactions in aqueous solutions. Some of these reactions are known to be markedly photo-sensitive either to visible or to ultra-violet light while others are only moderately so.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experiments were carried out as follows: A 500 c.p. Point-o-lite lamp was used as the source of illumination. The reactions took place in a beaker which was placed at a measured distance apart from the source of light. The light was switched on as soon as the reactants were mixed together and after a few minutes' exposure it was turned off. The beaker was immediately removed to complete darkness, 5 c.c. of the mixture withdrawn and the amount of change in it determined by titration. Further readings were continued to be taken by thus placing the reacting system in darkness. The reacting mixtures were again mixed together in a beaker identically as before but this time instead of exposing the system to the Point-o-lite lamp for the first few minutes it was kept all along in the dark and readings taken at intervals.

The following experimental results are obtained and they are of a preliminary nature. The unimolecular coefficients have always been calculated from the beginning of the reactions.

TABLE I

*Potassium Oxalate and Iodine at 32°C.**N/10-Potassium Oxalate and N/137-Iodine.*

Distance from the source of light = 21 cm.

Exposed to light for 5 minutes and then removed to darkness			In the dark throughout		
<i>t</i> (minutes)	$\alpha - x$ (c.c.)	k_1 (unimolecular)	<i>t</i> (minutes)	$\alpha - x$ (c.c.)	k_1 (unimolecular)
0	7.3		0	7.3	
5	6.5	.0101	7½	6.7	.00496
15	5.75	.00691	20	5.9	.00482
30	4.65	.00653	40	4.65	.00489
	Mean =	.00672		Mean =	.00482

TABLE II

*Tartaric Acid and Bromine at 32°C.**N/10-Tartaric acid and N/111.2-Bromine.*

Distance from the Point-o-lite lamp = 21 cm.

Exposed to light for 5 minutes and then removed to darkness			In the dark throughout		
<i>t</i>	$\alpha - x$	k_1	<i>t</i>	$\alpha - x$	k_1
0	9.0		0	9.0	
5	8.9	.0726	5	7.8	.0124
12	2.5	.0484	12	6.7	.0107
20	1.0	.0477	20	4.1	.0171
	Mean =	.0471		Mean =	.0134

TABLE III

*Lactic Acid and Bromine at 32° C.**N/10-Lactic acid and N/125-Bromine.*

Distance from the Point-o-lite lamp = 21 cm.

Exposed to light for 5 minutes and then removed to darkness			In the dark throughout		
<i>t</i>	<i>a-s</i>	<i>k₁</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>a-s</i>	<i>k₁</i>
0	8.0		0	8.0	
5	4.35	.0529	6	6.4	.0162
12	2.7	.0393	15	4.1	.0194
20	1.5	.0364	30	1.8	.0216
	Mean =	.0379		Mean =	.0191

TABLE IV

*Malic Acid and Bromine at 32° C.**N/10-Malic acid and N/125-Bromine.*

Distance from the Point-o-lite lamp = 21 cm.

Exposed to light for 5 minutes and then removed to darkness			In the dark throughout		
<i>t</i>	<i>a-s</i>	<i>k₁</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>a-s</i>	<i>k₁</i>
0	8.0		0	8.0	
5	3.35	.0756	5	6.0	.0249
12	2.3	.0451	12	4.5	.0209
16	1.4	.0421	25	2.2	.0224
	Mean =	.0436		Mean =	.0227

TABLE V

*Oxalic Acid and Bromine at 32°C.**N/10-Oxalic acid and N/111·2-Bromine.*

Distance from the Point-o-lite lamp = 27 cm.

Exposed to light for 5 minutes and then removed to darkness			In the dark throughout		
<i>t</i>	<i>a-s</i>	<i>k</i> ₁	<i>t</i>	<i>a-s</i>	<i>k</i> ₁
0	9·0		0	9·0	
5	1·9	·1351	6	8·3	·0726
12	0·75	·0899	12	1·3	·0702
20	0·2	·0828	20	0·45	·0651
	Mean =	·0864		Mean =	·0693

TABLE VI

*Citric Acid and Bromine at 32°C.**N/10-Citric acid and N/136-Bromine.*

Distance from the Point-o-lite lamp = 21 cm.

Exposed to light for 5 minutes and then removed to darkness			In the dark throughout		
<i>t</i>	<i>a-s</i>	<i>k</i> ₁	<i>t</i>	<i>a-s</i>	<i>k</i> ₁
0	8·4		0	8·4	
5	6·25	·0257	9½	5·8	·0171
15	4·2	·0202	20	3·75	·0175
30	2·3	·0188	35	2·0	·0170
	Mean =	·0195		Mean =	·0172

TABLE VII

Potassium Formate and Iodine at 32°C.

N/6.4-Potassium formate and N/100-Iodine.
 Distance from the Point-o-lite lamp = 21 cm.

Exposed to light for 5 minutes and then removed to darkness			In the dark throughout		
<i>t</i>	<i>a-s</i>	<i>k₁</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>a-s</i>	<i>k₁</i>
0	10.0		0	10.0	
5	7.0	.0809	5	7.9	.0206
12	5.6	.0209	12	5.8	.0200
20	3.6	.0222	20	3.9	.0206
	Mean =	.0216		Mean =	.0206

TABLE VIII

Sodium Citrate and Iodine at 32°C.

N/11.6-Sodium citrate and N/137-Iodine.
 Distance from the Point-o-lite lamp = 21 cm.

Exposed to light for 5 minutes and then removed to darkness			In the dark throughout		
<i>t</i>	<i>a-s</i>	<i>k₁</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>a-s</i>	<i>k₁</i>
0	7.3		0	7.3	
5	5.8	.0200	5	6.3	.0680
15	5.1	.0104	25	5.1	.0682
30	4.4	.00733	45	3.7	.0655
	Mean =	.0686		Mean =	.0688

TABLE IX

Oxalic Acid, Chromic Acid, Manganous Sulphate and Sulphuric Acid at 32° C.

N/30-Oxalic acid, N/517·2-Chromic acid, N/11·4-Sulphuric acid, N/600-Manganous sulphate.

Distance from the Point-o-lite lamp = 21 cm.

Exposed to light for 3 minutes and then removed to darkness			In the dark throughout		
t	$a-s$	$k_0 = s/t$	t	$a-s$	$k_0 = s/t$
0	9·8		0	9·8	
3	7·8	·50	3½	8·05	·36
8	6·05	·41	8	6·5	·35
12½	5·3	·47	13	4·7	·35
	Mean =	0·44		Mean =	0·353

TABLE X

Oxalic Acid, Potassium Permanganate, Manganous Sulphate and Sulphuric Acid at 32° C.

N/30-Oxalic acid, N/506·4-Potassium permanganate, N/600-Manganous sulphate and N/11·4-Sulphuric acid.

Distance from the Point-o-lite lamp = 21 cm.

Exposed to light for 45 seconds and then removed to darkness			In the dark throughout		
t	$a-s$	k_1	t	$a-s$	k_1
0	7·95		0	7·95	
½	5·5	·210	1½	4·1	·192
1½	4·2	·185	3	2·35	·176
3	3·2	·180	4	2·1	·145
	Mean =	·183		Mean =	·171

TABLE XI

*Potassium Persulphate and Potassium Iodide at 32°.**N/12-Potassium iodide and N/100-Potassium persulphate exposed to moderately bright sunlight.*

Exposed to sunlight for 1 minute and then removed to darkness			In the dark throughout		
<i>t</i>	<i>a-x</i>	$k_0 = a/t$	<i>t</i>	<i>a-x</i>	$k_0 = a/t$
0	0		0	0	
1	2.4	2.4	1½	2.5	1.667
3½	6.2	1.807	4½	7.2	1.694
5	9.4	1.860	6	10.2	1.700
		Mean = 1.894			Mean = 1.687

It is well known that the reaction between ferric chloride and ammonium oxalate is very sensitive to sunlight so this reaction, too, was studied to test if there existed any after-effect of illumination. Some ferric chloride, a larger quantity of ammonium oxalate and a few crystals of oxalic acid were mixed together and divided into two portions. One portion was exposed to bright sunlight while the other was kept in total darkness. The portion exposed to the sun began to show a precipitate of ferrous oxalate in about 10 minutes. As soon as the precipitate began to come out, the solution was removed to a dark room and filtered through double filter paper. The clean filtrate was now kept in total darkness and in about half-an-hour quite a large amount of precipitate was noted in this filtrate. The other portion of the original mixture which had been kept in the dark showed no formation of precipitate even after a much longer period.

It is evident that all the reactions investigated above are accelerated to a certain extent by the light from a Point-o-lite lamp and it is to be observed that all these light-sensitive reactions when once exposed to the light

for the first few moments proceed (in the absence of the light) with an appreciably greater velocity than in the case when the reactions take place all along in the dark. It should be noted that the foregoing results are only of a comparative nature.

The following figures will show the amount of acceleration caused by the light as well as the corresponding increase in the velocity of the reactions after the Point-o-light lamp has ceased to work over the velocity of the reactions proceeding all along in the dark.

TABLE XII

Reaction	Acceleration in the velocity produced by light	Ratio of the velocity of the dark reaction after the light has ceased to work to the velocity of the reaction in the dark all along
Tartaric acid and Bromine (Table II) ...	5.4 times	$\frac{.047}{.013} = 3.7$
Lactic acid and Bromine (Table III) ...	3.2 "	$\frac{.088}{.019} = 2.0$
Malic acid and Bromine (Table IV) ...	3.2 "	$\frac{.044}{.023} = 1.95$
Sodium citrate and Iodine (Table VIII) ...	2.9 "	$\frac{.0089}{.0069} = 1.3$
Potassium oxalate and Iodine (Table I) ...	2.1 "	$\frac{.0067}{.0048} = 1.4$
Oxalic acid and Bromine (Table V) ...	1.9 "	$\frac{.087}{.070} = 1.2$
Citric acid and Bromine (Table VI) ...	1.5 "	$\frac{.019}{.017} = 1.1$
Potassium formate and Iodine (Table VII) ...	1.5 "	$\frac{.022}{.020} = 1.1$
Oxalic acid, Chromic acid, Manganous sulphate and Sulphuric acid (Table IX).	1.43 "	$\frac{.44}{.35} = 1.23$
Potassium persulphate and Potassium iodide (Table XI).	1.42 "	$\frac{1.90}{1.69} = 1.13$
Oxalic acid, Potassium permanganate, Manganous sulphate and Sulphuric acid (Table X).	1.2 "	$\frac{.183}{.171} = 1.07$

From the above table it is at once evident that there exists a proportionality between the ratio of the velocity of a reaction in the dark after the light has ceased to work to the velocity of the reaction throughout in the dark and the corresponding acceleration of the velocity of the reaction by the light. In other words, the greater the acceleration caused by the light the greater is the after-effect produced in the reaction.

Among the reactions investigated by us we observed a few cases, which, in spite of being markedly photosensitive, exhibit no after-effect. The reaction between sodium potassium tartrate and bromine is accelerated by light yet the ratio of the velocity of the reaction in the dark after the light has ceased to work to the velocity in the dark all along remains almost unity. A mixture of mercuric chloride and ammonium oxalate was exposed to sunlight and just when some calomel began to form, it was filtered off and the filtrate kept in a dark room. No further precipitation of calomel took place in the filtrate in the dark. Again the decompositions of Fehling's solution and a mixture of an oxalate and copper sulphate solution take place readily in strong sunlight, and deposit of copper is obtained but in none of these cases any after-effect was observed after illumination.

It is very difficult to explain the after-effect in photochemical reactions and no satisfactory suggestion in explaining this phenomenon has yet been advanced.

We shall cite certain facts which are more or less allied to these photochemical after-effects. Phillips (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1913, 89, 42) exposed mercury vapour in a quartz tube to radiations containing $\lambda=2537\text{\AA}$ from a mercury lamp. He found that the mercury vapour began to fluoresce and he observed that the glow passed up the tube and spread out to a distance of 18 inches from the place of illumination.

In a previous paper (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 141, 1) we have suggested the explanation of this observation of Phillips in the following way:—

The atoms of mercury in the mercury vapour become activated by the absorption of light $\lambda = 2537\text{\AA}$. The activated atoms in losing the extra amount of energy can give out radiation and can emit the glow. Now, the activated atom in coming in contact with an inactive atom which has not been illuminated can impart its energy to the inactive atom and activate it. This process can repeat itself and a long column of mercury vapour becomes activated and gives a glow though not illuminated. Though the life period of an activated atom or molecule is of the order 10^{-8} second it seems probable that by these collisions the glow can continue to a much longer period.

It was observed originally by Stark (*Ann. Phys.*, 1904, 14, 520) that a stream of mercury vapour, allowed to distil away from the arc or glow discharge in vacuo, remains luminous. It may be said to carry the luminosity away with it and in the case of the arc discharge there is no difficulty in detecting the luminosity for 50 cm. or so from the source.

Lord Rayleigh has obtained more or less similar results (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1914, A 90, 364; 1914, 91, 92; 1925, 108, 262). Consequently, there is absolutely no doubt in the fact that light persists in the vapour even after the source of excitation has been removed and this is exactly a phenomenon of the same nature as the after-effect in photochemical reactions, and we are of the opinion that the cause of both the phenomena would be identical. It seems possible in photochemical reactions that on illumination some of the molecules of the reacting substances become activated and these activated molecules by impact can activate other inactive molecules and this process is likely to take time and consequently, even when the source of

illumination is removed, the activated molecules take some time to die out and hence the chemical action persists for a short time even after the illumination is cut off.

Franck and Grotrian (*Z. Physik*, 1921, 4, 89) have repeated the experiment of Phillips and have accounted for the persistence of the luminosity by supposing that the excited atoms, which have absorbed $\lambda = 2537\text{\AA}$ and are prepared to re-emit this line, unite with other mercury atoms to form molecules. When these molecules are again dissociated the stored energy can be liberated and $\lambda = 2537\text{\AA}$ is emitted.

Several years ago Weigert (*Ann. Physik*, 1907, 24, 243) threw out the suggestion that a photo-chemical change may consist in the intramolecular transformation of the molecules of the light-absorbing substance or in the formation of molecular complexes which act as reaction-nuclei under illumination. It is needless to say that there is hardly any experimental support to these conjectures. Similarly, for lack of experimental support this phenomenon of after-effect cannot be associated with the existence of chain reactions or intermediate-compound formations. That a series of frequencies is active in a chemical change is explained by Perrin (*Ann. Physique*, 1919, 11, 1; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1922, 17, 547) and by Lewis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 613) by assuming that such reactions take place in steps with the formation of intermediate compounds. Though it may be true in a few cases yet in the majority of reactions the validity of this assumption cannot be experimentally proved. The very recent developments of the "activation theory" seem to do away with the necessity of such arguments.

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